

TRIQUERTA: Towards next generation risk assessment and mitigation of climate change and natural hazards threatening cultural heritage

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Cultural heritage (CH) sites face increasing risks from climate change (CC) and various hazards, posing threats such as rising sea levels, extreme weather events, and environmental degradation, endangering their preservation and long-term existence. A lot of research has been done on protecting CH sites, but we still lack systemic approaches towards identifying and mitigating risks to CH sites. The TRIQUERTA EU research project proposes a technological toolbox and a methodological framework for tackling climate change risks and natural hazards threatening CH, in the most efficient way possible. The main strategic objectives of TRIQUERTA include: the creation of a repository of knowledge on effects of CC and natural hazards on CH, including lessons learnt from existing mitigation measures; the implementation of a systemic approach towards identification of upcoming risks and hazards to CH; and the usage of novel technologies allowing efficient and accurate quantification of threats to CH.

The TRIQUERTA project's methodology is structured around three fundamental stages: (i) identifying risks, (ii) quantifying risks, and (iii) mitigating risks, forming what is known as the "trifecta" approach. This approach constructs a robust framework for evaluating and addressing the following categories of risks: (i) climate-related risks; (ii) extreme water, snow and ice hazard risks; (iii) geological and geophysical risks; and (iv) chemical and biological hazard risks. Furthermore, it assesses the damage and failure modes of CH structures as well as the compounded effects of various environmental stressors on CH sites. TRIQUERTA will be validated in eight different CH sites across Europe. The main project results can be summarized as follows:

- a novel risk quantification framework for CH sites;
- an expanded knowledge base platform;

- a decision-support platform (TRIQUETRA DSS) including risk severity quantification tools and mitigation measure selection and optimization tools;
- novel protective materials;
- a novel flash LiDAR;
- water quality analysers; and
- a CH site digitization framework.